

Role of Research in the Development of Chemical Industry*

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Chemical process industries are one of the most complex industries which draw their supplies of raw materials from mines, forests, sea, air, oil, gas wells, and farms. Besides, they spark the growth areas in many other industries. A number of products such as basic industrial chemicals including heavy inorganic and organic chemicals, synthetic resins and plastics, synthetic rubber, synthetic fibres, ammunition, explosives, dyestuffs and dyes, industrial gases, fertilizers, vegetable oils, paints, varnishes and lacquers, fine chemicals including drugs and pharmaceuticals, essential oils and their isolates, perfumes, cosmetics and other toilet preparations, soaps and detergents, matches, and a host of miscellaneous chemicals such as insecticides, fungicides, weedicides, textile auxiliaries, glue and gelatine fluxes come under the purview of chemical industry. Thus, the industry serves the fundamental human needs—food, clothing, shelter, health, transportation, communication, etc.

Naturally, chemical industry has become the most dynamic segment of the economy in the growth and progress of countries. It is now well on its way to becoming one of the most important activities in the economy as a whole of the advanced countries. The secret of this dynamism lies mainly in continuous research orientation of the industry. It is also the most important industry for ensuring national safety.

The industry, which is characterized by a certain complexity and high capital investment per employee, depends more than any other sector of the economy upon a large proportion of scientific personnel. The spectacular and sometimes explosive development in the industry abroad has been due to competition of several types, such as inter-commodity competition, inter-process competition, inter-industry competition, and inter-end product competition. The same chemical can be manufactured from alternative raw materials and by different processes, so much so that chemical industry equipment becomes fast obsolete. There is an in-built problem in the chemical plant industry of unpredictable technical changes. For instance, the ammonia plant built by the Imperial Chemical Industries in U.K. twenty years ago was the Company's 'pride and joy'. But sometime back the plant became obsolete and was being replaced. Before its modernization had been completed, however, the naphtha reforming process developed by the Company proved to have outweighing advantages and so the whole of the "new" plant had to be scrapped.

The birth of organized chemical industry in India dates back to 1890 when the first plant for manufacture of sulphuric acid was set up in Kammagar, Dist. Hooghly, Bengal

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by D' Waldie. In the initial stages, the development of the industry was almost wholly through private enterprise, often to meet specific needs. The two world wars provided a stimulus to the Indian industry. But with the attainment of independence, the rate of development has been gaining under the successive Five Year Plans. From the emphasis in the First Plan on maximising the utilisation of existing capacities, improving the efficiency of the units in operation, and creating additional new production capacities in a very few selected industries, we are today implementing a programme which aims at achieving a self-sustaining economy that should serve as the basis for an industrial edifice approaching that in many industrially advanced countries.

Thus, the capital investment in the industry moved from Rs 27 crores during the First Plan to Rs 140 crores during the Second Plan and the productive capital for 1963 was Rs 375 crores in the large-scale sector. An idea as to the size of the chemical industry can also be had from the fact that the value of chemicals and chemical products produced in the large-scale sector in the country amounted to Rs 260 crores in this year. The target set for the Third Plan is Rs 877 crores and for the Fourth Plan Rs 1,600 crores, nearly 31 per cent of the total investment in the manufacturing industries in the organised sector. The industry attained during the Third Plan a rate growth of 10 per cent as compared to the overall rate of economic growth of 5 per cent.

Research for the chemical industries in all advanced countries in particular has been carried out mainly by the industries themselves as there has been not only national but international competition between them in respect of production of quality products at low cost. Naturally, tremendous advance has been made in chemical technology through their research effort and many break-throughs have been possible. For example, in the Journal 'Chemical Engineering', a formidable list of processes and products, which have been developed as a result of research effort, is given every six months.

But in India chemical industries of such magnitude are not in existence and organised industrial research has been only twenty-five years old. But due recognition to the importance of chemical research has been given by the Council of Scientific & Industrial Research in that the first national laboratory to be established by the Council is the National Chemical Laboratory. At present, besides this laboratory, the Regional Research Laboratory, Hyderabad, the Central Electrochemical Research Institute, Karaikudi, the Central Salt and Marine Chemicals Research Institute, Bhavnagar, and the Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow are actively engaged in research for the chemical industry. Consequent on the Government taking up in a big way exploration of oil and helping the setting up of oil refineries and petrochemical complexes in various regions of the country, the Indian Institute of Petroleum has also been functioning at Dohra Dun. It is a happy augury that finding oil has also coincided with the plans of setting up of petrochemical complexes in the country. Throughout the world, the greater availability of petroleum feed stocks as an alternative to conventional raw materials has resulted in introduction of new processes, such as (i) partial oxidation and steam reformation of petroleum naphtha for making ammonia, (ii) substitution of cheaper ethylene obtained by naphtha cracking for production of C_2 , C_3 , and C_4 hydrocarbons in place of carbide-based acetylene for organic synthesis, and (iii) recovery of aromatics during petroleum refining, have revolutionized the chemical industry and made it possible to change over from conventional feed stocks and development of integrated plants.

The part that research can play in the development of Indian chemical industry can be grouped under the following heads:

- (1) Improvements in manufacturing techniques and quality of chemical raw materials, products, and services with the object of improving productivity and reducing cost.
- (2) Continuous endeavour to develop new processes, products, and services to offset obsolescence.
- (3) Reduction in operating and maintenance cost of plants and equipments.
- (4) Discovering new uses for existing materials, products, and processes.
- (5) Development of cheaper and indigenous substitutes for costly and imported materials.
- (6) Finding use for by-products and chemical wastes.
- (7) Standardisation of products and practices.

It is not possible to recount the benefits which have accrued to the chemical industry through indigenous research effort. Some of the significant results emerging from the Council's laboratories may be mentioned here by way of illustration. In respect of the survey of raw materials for the chemical industry, high grade limestones occurring in various parts of the country have been surveyed and their suitability for use in various chemical industries have been assessed by the National Chemical Laboratory. The results, which have been published, are of value to user industries. Survey of glass sands and clays, carried out by the Central Glass & Ceramic Research Institute, has proved to be of value for the glass industry.

Resins from cashewnut shell liquid, cuprous oxide, boron-free enamels, liquid rubber, nicotine sulphate, carbion, resins from tar oil fraction, foaming agent for concrete, basic magnesium carbonate, active carbon, and sodium azide are examples of products manufactured in the country by processes evolved in national laboratories. Besides, a large number of processes and products have been licensed for commercial production.

Utilization of by-products and wastes has also received attention. The process for the production of wax from sisal waste, worked out at the National Chemical Laboratory, is being used. The technique of wet grinding of mica waste, carried out by the Central Glass & Ceramic Research Institute, can be used for making paints and greases. Hydrofluosilicic acid, obtained as a by-product from superphosphate manufacture, has been used as a raw material for the production of synthetic cryolite which is imported for aluminium manufacture. Tar oil fractions have been utilized for the production of resins needed for the manufacture of hardboards from waste cellulose materials.

The present emergency has offered a challenge to the Indian research worker for making the country self-reliant by finding out satisfactory substitutes for imported materials. The total value of annual imports in respect of all chemicals is of the order of Rs 91 crores. The Council has given utmost consideration to this problem and is reorienting its research programmes in which sufficient importance is given to import substitution; elimination. Of the total projects in all the national laboratories of over 1600, in excess of 350 projects are in respect of this category. Out of these, mention may be made of the following under the purview of the chemical industry: Development of filter aids, production of cellulose tri-acetate from cotton linters, ferro-chrome, lignosulphonates and petro sur-

factants for use in drilling, zircon opacifiers, luminescent phosphors, 2,4-dichlorophenols, nitrophenol, cadmium sulphate orange, X-ray grade barium sulphate are but a few. But special mention must be made of the method of recovery of potassium chloride from sea bitters, worked out by the Central Salt and Marine Chemicals Research Institute, as all the potassium chloride required for fertilizer purposes is imported at present. One other project, which is particularly important, is that the phosphate required for manufacture of phosphatic fertilizers is at present imported. It is proposed to explore the possibility of recovering phosphates from marine resources.

The import list for chemicals can be broadly classified into:

- (i) Items which are being produced in the country and production of which is not adequate.
- (ii) Items which require small assistance of research and designing.
- (iii) Items which can be substituted, without much difficulty, to a large extent.
- (iv) Items for which regular research and development work are required.
- (v) Items which must be imported for strategic or economic reasons over a long period.

In the first three classes of items, self-sufficiency can be acquired in a period of one to two years and substantial foreign exchange can be saved with earnest co-operation of research and industry. For items of class four, a regular research programme may have to be formulated.

It may be worthwhile mentioning another step which the Council has taken to be of help, particularly to the chemical industry. It has recently set up a Technical Information Centre at Bombay to act as an intermediary between the national laboratories and the chemical and allied industries in regard to supply of technical information and arranging for solution of the technical problems of the industry by appropriate national laboratories. It is hoped that this step will go a long way in bringing the chemical industry and the research laboratories closer for their mutual benefit. The recent 'get-together' between scientists and representatives of industry, organised by the Council, is yet another step which would enable a better awareness of the problems and difficulties of the industry by the scientists and appreciation by the industry of the role of scientific research in industrial development.

It may be mentioned at this stage that development of process know-how alone would not lead to the development of the infrastructure required for making the chemical industry self-dependent. Research on design and engineering of chemical plants should be undertaken in a big way to fill the gap between laboratory and pilot plant researches and the industrial upscaling to commercial size plants. Due attention has been given by the Council to this aspect and a Design and Engineering Unit has been set up for the purpose.

The application of the results of research in the less-developed countries has problems peculiar to the stage of the development of the country itself. The extent and speed of utilization of research is partly a function of the country's industrial growth—the higher the stage of industrial growth and science consciousness in the country, the greater the chances of the speedy utilization of the results of research. More and more of research would be required and utilized as the industries in the country grow and diversify. At the same time scientific and technological research has to be oriented to suit the needs of the

country by taking cognizance of the plans and programmes of industrial development. Research programming should be based on closer links with economic factors, such as imports, exports, items for manufacture proposed to be undertaken by the industrial companies and public sector projects. For this, mechanism and arrangements must be devised for making available detailed data on individual items. At the outset it is necessary to prepare a hand-book of raw materials required for each and every chemical industry for ton of the product, their present availability and their sources, the by-products of each of the factories, etc. and necessary market research data and statistics. Laboratories could so frame their programmes as to result in immediate benefit to industry. A decision could also be made by the laboratories as to what needs to be imported by way of technology and what could be developed within the country.

The maximum results from research can be achieved only when research is closely integrated with planning and becomes a part of the process of planning and development. Already it is taking place to some extent and this must happen even more.

Research in chemical technology needs personnel trained in the whole spectrum of technologists from the chemist to the mechanical engineer. I am afraid that the present method of training followed in the country does not produce the right type of persons for undertaking research in chemical technology. A few universities have courses of study leading to industrial chemistry, chemical technology and many universities have courses leading to chemical engineering. The industrial chemist or chemical technologist is biased towards unit processes and the chemical engineer towards unit operations. Applied chemistry is a field which is in between and has not found favour in academic circles in India. The study of this interdisciplinary region is of vital importance to the chemical industry. Its neglect even in U.K. has been ascribed in the McLeod Report as the main research for the small number of new chemical processes developed recently in U.K. on a technical scale.

Further, in regard to the content of chemical engineering courses, apart from its bias towards chemistry or mechanical engineering along with coverage of basic principles, newer developments, such as instrumentation and automation, are not being covered. Czechoslovakia and Russia are the only two countries which provide for this study after the general part of the undergraduate course, arranged specifically to the chemical industry. Also instruction in computers is included. It is appropriate to add in this context that students of science, who have had practical knowledge of chemical industry, would prove to be better fitted for research work. In this context, it may be worthwhile mentioning that in France the Institut du Genie Chimique at Toulouse has established two small chemical factories, a contact sulphuric acid plant and a nitric acid plant by catalytic oxidation to provide realistic plant experience to science undergraduates.

The other requirement for a research worker in the chemical industry is a knowledge of economics. Economics applied to chemical industry is a speciality subject after a basic course in chemistry and chemical engineering in Prague. Technologists with a thorough grasp of economics could well prove to be the ideal research workers for undertaking research in chemical industry. In India, we need more and more personnel of this type to make a break-through in the field of chemical technology.